

NEP 2020: AN OVERVIEW ON POLICY AND PROVISIONS FOR PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND SPORTS

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Abstract

Education has been acknowledged as one of the potential instrument of social change and important means of bringing about national development. Education can no longer be considered merely a vast as of mental acrobatics but has to help in developing an individual who is physically, mentally sound .emotionally balanced and socially adjusted to all.

“Soul without body, mind without matter and education without movement are meaningless concept.”

Every human being has a fundamental right of access to education as well as physical education and sport that’s why physical education is the most democratic subject. Two years before CBSE has taken decision of experimental, experiential learning with integration of physical education.

Physical education should be integral part of education system for holistic development of child. Physical education can provide the right direction and necessary action to improve the health of people in every community, society, nation and even the world.

Vision of NEP2020 is directly concerns with nation’s sustainability into an equitable bivariate knowledge of society. The new education policy is bringing drastic change in physical education and sports by eliminating the difference or gap between curricular and extra-curricular activities by giving equal weightage other subjects like science and English. Along with emotional, educational development physical and mental development is very necessary for overall development of child. Physical education is an activity-based approach that focuses on learning by doing. Activity is the link between education and physical education which emphasize great focus on all –round development of child.

How physical education helps to make education equitable, Qualitable the concept sound mind and sound body is successful when we integrate physical education in main curriculum and in teaching learning process for mental, emotional and physical development of child.

Nowadays our country moving towards sporting nation we all observed Olympic and Para-Olympic performances which motivates young talents of our country.

Keywords: *NEP2020, Policies and Provisions for physical education, holistic development of child and benefits in daily life.*

Objectives:

- 1) To understand the provisions and policies regarding physical education.
- 2) To be acquainted with importance of policies and provisions of physical education.

Keywords: *National Education Policy, Physical Education, Holistic Development of child and recommendations from NEP2020*

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Introduction: Physical education is an activity-based approach that focuses on learning by doing. Activity is the link between education and physical education. NEP2020 incorporates sports and physical education as an integral and important part of education in undergraduate, primary and secondary education. Educators and administrators can use physical education as a teaching tool to achieve all the key principles and outcomes foreseen in NEP..

The focus of national education policy as far as the area of Curriculum is concerned as far as a whole goal of the policy is concerned it is 21st century skills yes policy is focusing on Holistic development of students by a developing 21st century skills in them and manifestation of knowledge and perfection for this is clearly stating that we have too many faces knowledge NEP2020 envisages sports as a part of the curriculum and lays emphasis on sports, physical education, integrated with learning, as well as adopting fitness as a lifelong attitude.

Aim of physical Education: All round development of child.

Physical Education: A curriculum quality physical education encourages all students to achieve success in sports world and other physically demanding activities. It is designed to give students the opportunity to become physically strong confident in a way that supports their health and fitness. Opportunities to compete and participate in sports and other activities help build character and instill values such as acceptance of failure and success along with respect.

Definition of Physical Education According to William, Physical education is the sum of man's physical activities selected as to kind and conducted as to outcomes." According to J.B. Nash, "Physical Education is that field of education which deals with big muscle activities and their related responses.

Physical education takes into consideration care and development of the human body. Focus on athletics and include hygiene. Curriculum elements addressing physical development, strength, body coordination and flexibility. Body organ and strength training to promote health and performance.

Holistic Development of child: Every child has certain unique characteristics. He or she may have different personality traits, interests, preferences, values, attitudes, strengths and weaknesses. The curriculum is designed to help each child find their place in the world according to their individuality. Achieving this holistic development of the child is of utmost importance.

A holistic approach to child development and learning recognizes the connection between mind, body and spirit. When educators and childcare professionals take a holistic approach, they pay attention to children's physical, personal, social, emotional and mental health, and cognitive aspects of learning. . A holistic approach to child development aims to simultaneously consider the physical, emotional, relational, intellectual and spiritual aspects of a child's life. The importance of a holistic approach is that children learn different skills at different stages. Walking, talking, motor skills, fine motor skills, etc. It can meet the demands and challenges of daily life.

NEP2020, Policies and Provisions:

In NEP2020 focus will be experiential learning, Art integrated learning, skills base learning and integration of sports. With combination of other school subjects, to achieve decided goals it will be focuses on competency based learning.

In Clause 4.8 NEP stated sports integration as a cross curricular pedagogical approach by implementation of this integration utilization in physical activities will enhances by which it develops national integration, citizenship, leadership, cooperation, collaboration, team spirit, self-initiative, self-direction and responsibility etc. Sports integration will help students in their physical growth and development under maintain them fit under “Fit India Movement” Sports integration foster holistic development of child.

Empower students through flexibility in their course choices:

Policy makers and stake holders have made many proposals to add another dimension to the popular education system. One of his is to give secondary students the flexibility to choose the subjects they want. It has been suggested that this is a characteristic of secondary education in which students are free to design their own course of study without being caught up in vertical structures such as the arts, humanities, and sciences.

Interdisciplinary and comprehensive education is one of the basic principles of NEP2020. Curriculum must include subjects such as science and social sciences, as well as subjects such as games, sports and fitness that provide a comprehensive, informative and enriching education.

NEP also suggests other ways to make it easier for students to participate in sports and other physical activities. This increases subject choice and flexibility, allowing students to opt physical education classes as part of their curriculum. The policy also proposes bagless days, which give students the opportunity to participate in local professional activities as well as other activities such as sports and gardening. In addition, NEP 2020 encourages the formation of clubs, including yoga, physical education and health, at the school, educational institution and district level.

Given the importance of health education in schools, NEP lists health and nutrition, sports, fitness, wellness, sports, hygiene and hygiene as key subjects, skills and abilities to be learned.

Healthy learning environments:

NEP develops measures to promote physical and mental health. This includes regular health check-ups at school, in particular to ensure 100% vaccination coverage, and health monitoring through health cards. Periodic medical examination for students. NEP 2020 also recommends reducing the weight of school bags and textbooks. For the mental, emotional health of children along with holistic change. To implement some of these reforms, NEP 2020 proposes the concept of school complexes that share resources such as infrastructure, teachers, counselors, sports equipment and equipment. In addition, a special short-term teacher training program allows you to update your skills and knowledge for teaching in schools with local vocations, knowledge and skills, including physical education.

Benefits of Physical Education:

- ✓ Knowledge of health
- ✓ Physical fitness
- ✓ Emotional development
- ✓ Cultural development
- ✓ Helps in creating discipline
- ✓ Develop leadership quality
- ✓ National integration
- ✓ Helps in developing human relations
- ✓ Expression of creativity

- ✓ International understanding
- ✓ Maintaining healthy bones and muscles
- ✓ Eradicating anxiety and depression
- ✓ Improving positive mental health
- ✓ Motivate a person forward positive life style
- ✓ Polishing cognitive skills
- ✓ Enhancing comprehension
- ✓ Encouraging better academic performance and achievements
- ✓ Boost energy level
- ✓ Helps in managing stress
- ✓ Improve self-image
- ✓ Improve motor skill develop
- ✓ Fueling Self-Confidence
- ✓ Social integration

Conclusion:

Physical Education is an integral part of life for holistic development of child NEP2020 proposes the certain provisions, along with required changes in curriculum. Exercise and sports gives the child more than just physical, social, moral and psychological well-being. Physical Education aims at educating students though physical activities. NEP2020 can bring a major change in perception requires orientations of policy makers, Stakeholders, curriculum developers, Teachers, educators, health workers society at large. Imbibing ethical and social values, the importance of health and fitness among children is very essential in present era for managing stress, academic pressure, anxiety Prevention of Juvenile Delinquencies, Suicidal deaths, Depression, Malnutrition. A well designed and structured curriculum in Physical Education will help in accomplishing the objectives of the school, holistic development of child and also aid in building a strong and prosperous nation.

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